

Synergic Extraction and Spectrophotometric Determination of Vanadium (V) with *N-p*-Tolylacetylmandelohydroxamic Acid in Presence of *o*-Methoxy Phenol*

B. S. CHANDRAVANSI and V. K. GUPTA**

Department of Chemistry, Ravishankar University, Raipur-492 002, M.P., India

Manuscript received 26 April 1978, revised 19 September 1978, accepted 6 October 1978.

Vanadium(V) reacts with *N-p*-tolylacetylmandelohydroxamic acid to form 1 : 2 (metal to ligand) complex, containing a basic V=O group. The basic group reacts with *o*-methoxyphenol to give a hyper and bathochromic effect in chloroform. On the basis of the high synergic effect of *o*-methoxyphenol, a selective and sensitive method for the extraction and spectrophotometric determination of vanadium(V) has been developed. The method has been successfully applied for the determination of vanadium in standard steel samples and in presence of several diverse ions.

THE V-OH group in vanadium-*N*-phenylbenzohydroxamate and 8-quinolinolate is acidic and is subjected to esterification in the presence of alcohols¹⁻⁴, giving rise to a hypsochromic effect. The V=O group in the same complex is basic and reacts with various acids including phenols⁵⁻⁶, producing a bathochromic effect. These reactions of vanadium complexes with various organic substances have led to the esterification method for determining alcohols⁷, to the method for detecting phenols⁸, based on adduct formation and to the synergic extraction and spectrophotometric determination of vanadium in the presence of phenols⁹.

N-p-Tolylacetylmandelohydroxamic acid is a typical monobasic and bidentate extracting agent, which readily extracts VO₂⁺ into chloroform from strong hydrochloric acid solution and form 1 : 2 (metal to ligand) complex, containing a basic V=O group. The basic group reacts with *o*-methoxyphenol to produce hyper and bathochromic effect in chloroform.

The present paper deals with the synergic extraction of vanadium-*N-p*-tolylacetylmandelohydroxamate in the presence of *o*-methoxyphenol. A sensitive method for the extraction and spectrophotometric determination of vanadium(V) in presence of *o*-methoxyphenol has been developed. The method has been applied to the determination of vanadium in standard steel samples and in presence of several diverse ions.

Experimental

Apparatus and reagents :

A Carl Zeiss UV VIS Specord recording spectrophotometer and EC Spectrophotometer model

* This paper was presented at the Annual Convention of Chemists, 1977 at Jaipur.

** To whom correspondence should be made.

GS-865 with 10 mm matched silica cells were used for the absorbance measurements.

N-p-Tolylacetylmandelohydroxamic acid was prepared by the condensation of acetylmandelylchloride⁹ and *p*-tolylhydroxylamine by reported method¹⁰ (m.p. 126°).

A stock solution of vanadium was prepared by dissolving analytical grade ammonium metavanadate in glass-distilled water. Vanadium content of the solution was determined volumetrically using potassium permanganate solution¹¹. A 0.01 *M* *N-p*-tolylacetylmandelohydroxamic acid solution was prepared in alcohol free chloroform. Solutions of diverse ions were prepared by dissolving analytical grade reagents following the procedure of West¹².

General procedure :

Transfer an aliquot of oxidized solution containing 0.02-0.2 mg of vanadium(V) to a separatory funnel and add distilled water and hydrochloric acid until the volume is about 25 ml and the acidity between 6.0 and 8.0 *M*. Add 5 ml of the reagent solution and shake for 1 min. Add 5 ml of 2.0 *M* chloroform solution of *o*-methoxyphenol and shake the mixture vigorously for 3 minutes. Collect the chloroform layer in a 25 ml volumetric flask. Wash the aqueous phase twice with 4 ml of chloroform, collect the washings in the same flask and then dilute to the mark with the chloroform. Measure the absorbance at 645 nm against the corresponding reagent blank.

Results and Discussion

Chloroform solution of *N-p*-tolylacetylmandelohydroxamic acid (*N-p*-TAMHA) extracts vanadium(V) from strong hydrochloric acid medium. The

wavelength of maximum absorption of the reddish-violet extract is 520 nm. When *o*-methoxyphenol is added to chloroform solution of vanadium *N-p*-TAMHA complex, the wavelength of maximum absorption shifts to longer wavelength and absorbance increases with increasing concentration of *o*-methoxyphenol. At higher concentration of *o*-methoxyphenol, more than 0.2*M*, the wavelength of maximum absorption (645 nm) and the absorbance remain constant.

Vanadium is completely extracted into chloroform from 6-8 *M* of hydrochloric acid irrespective of the absence or presence of *o*-methoxyphenol.

The blue adduct of vanadium is extracted into chloroform within 3 min. and the extracts are stable for 48 hours. Variation in temperature of the aqueous phase from 20° to 40° did not produce any measurable change in the absorbance of the chloroform extract.

The absorbances increase rapidly as the mole ratio of reagent to vanadium(V) is increased from 1 : 1 to 8 : 1, from the ratios of 8 : 1 to 100 : 1, absorbances remained constant.

Beer's law is obeyed in the concentration range 1-8 μg of vanadium per ml. The optimum concentration range evaluated from Ringbom's curve¹³ is 1.7-6.3 ppm. The relative error per 1% absolute photometric error evaluated from Ayres's equation¹⁴ is 2.85%. The relative standard deviation calculated from ten repeated determinations of solutions containing 100 μg V per 25 ml is $\pm 0.5\%$. Sandell's sensitivity is 0.0085 μg V cm^{-2} .

The molar absorptivity of the vanadium-*N-p*-TAMHA complex is 4050 ± 50 l. mole⁻¹ cm⁻¹ (λ_{max} 520 nm), while in the presence of *o*-methoxyphenol, molar absorptivity is 5950 ± 50 l. mole⁻¹ cm⁻¹ (λ_{max} 645 nm), i.e., synergic extraction of vanadium-*N-p*-tolylacetylmandelohydroxamate is observed in the presence of *o*-methoxyphenol.

For determining the composition of the vanadium-*N-p*-TAMHA-*o*-methoxyphenol adduct, two series of experiments were carried out. In one experiment the concentration of *o*-methoxyphenol was kept constantly in excess and the ratio of vanadium(V) to *N-p*-TAMHA was determined by Job's method of continuous variation. The result obtained indicate the ratio of V : *N-p*-TAMHA is 1 : 2. In the second experiment, the concentration of vanadium(V) and *N-p*-TAMHA were kept constant and the concentration of *o*-methoxyphenol was varied. In this experiment the distribution ratio is a function of the concentration of *o*-methoxyphenol in chloroform. However, it is difficult to determine the composition of the complex by log-log plot of partition, because slow attainment of the extraction equilibrium and possible decomposition of the adduct in strong acidic media.

For studying the effect of diverse ions in the determination of vanadium, the general procedure was followed. The following ions do not interfere Al(III), Ba(II), Be(II), Ca(II), Cd(II), Ce(IV), Co(II), Cr(III), Cu(II), Fe(III), Mg(II), Hg(II), Mn(II), Ni(II), Sn(IV), Sr(II), Th(IV), Tl(I), U(VI), Zn(II), acetate, nitrate, perchlorate, tartrate and sulphate.

Mo(VI) and W(VI) interfere. Ti(IV) and Zr(IV) which interfere in the determination of vanadium with other hydroxamic acids did not interfere upto 400 ppm with *N-p*-TAMHA.

Determination of Vanadium in steel :

The vanadium(V) was estimated in British Chemical Standard steels. Two tungsten-vanadium steels, 64 a and 241/1 and a tungsten free low alloy steel, 252, were taken for the analysis of vanadium.

The general method for treating vanadium containing material depends upon the nature and composition of the sample¹⁵.

Treat a known amount of steel containing about 1 mg of vanadium with 10-12 ml of 6*N* sulphuric acid in a 250 ml beaker. Heat gently till all action ceases, adding more acid if necessary. Cautiously add concentrated nitric acid to oxidise vanadium to their highest oxidation state and to convert the tungsten into bright yellow tungstic acid. Heat gently at first then strongly till all particles disappear. The solution should not be evaporated to dryness because appreciable amount of vanadium are carried down by tungstic acid¹⁶. Cool, dilute to 25 ml, filter off the precipitate on a sintered glass crucible and wash several times with hot water and 0.1 *N* sulphuric acid. Dilute the filtrate to 100 ml into a volumetric flask.

In case of tungsten free steel filtration is not necessary.

An aliquot of the steel solution, as prepared above, was taken and the vanadium content was determined by general procedure. The results are given in Table-1.

TABLE-1 DETERMINATION OF VANADIUM IN B. C. S. STEEL

B.C.S. Steel No.	Vanadium found* %	Certified value %	Relative standard deviation %
64 a Alloy steel	1.550	1.57	± 0.54
241/1 High speed steel	1.540	1.57	± 0.63
252 Low alloy steel	0.455	0.46	± 0.50

*Average of 3 values.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Prof. S. G. Tandon, Head, Department of Chemistry, Ravishankar University Raipur, for providing facilities and one of them (B. S. Chandravanshi) is thankful to U.G.C., New Delhi for the award of a fellowship.

References

1. N. KURMAIAH, D. SATYANARAYANA and V. PANDU RANGA RAO, *Talanta*, 1967, 14, 495.
2. H. KAWAMOTO and H. AKAIWA, *Nippon Kagaku Zasshi*, 1973, 94, 90.
3. I. KOJIMA and M. TANAKA, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1975, 75, 367.
4. I. KOJIMA and Y. MIWA, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1976, 83, 329.
5. A. J. BLAIR and D.A. PANTONY, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1955, 13, 1.
6. F. BUSCARONS, J. L. MARIN and J. CLAVER, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1958, 3, 310.
7. M. TANAKA and I. KOJIMA, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1968, 41, 75 and paper cited therein.
8. I. M. KORENMAN, V. G. GANINA, G. R. BARANCHIKOVA and V. L. ZYUZINA, *Tr. Khim. Tekhanol.*, 1969, 124, Chem. Abs. 1971, 74, 9418c.
9. GILMAN BLATT, "Organic Synthesis Collective", Second Ed., Vol. I, p. 12.
10. V. K. GUPTA and S. G. TANDON, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1971, 48, 753.
11. W. F. HILLEBRAND, G. E. F. LUNDELL, H. A. BRIGHT and J. I. HOFFMAN, "Applied Inorganic Analysis", Wiley, New York, 1953, 2nd Ed., p. 458.
12. P. W. WEST, *J. Chem. Educ.* 1941, 18, 528.
13. A. RINGBOM, *Z. Anal. Chem.*, 1938/39, 115, 332.
14. G. H. AYRES, *Anal. Chem.*, 1949, 21, 652.
15. F. D. SNELL and G. T. SNELL, "Calorimetric Methods of Analysis", D. VAN NOSTRAND Co. Inc. New York, 1949, Vol. II, Chapter 24.
16. S. G. CLARKE, *Analyst*, 1927, 52, 466.